

Experimental validation of two-section ridge and tapered lasers for the design of a monolithically mode-locked 200pJ source at 900 nm for two-photon excitation fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy

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ABSTRACT

We present a new monolithic multi-section laser diode concept for two-photon excitation microscopy (2ph-FLIM). This work is carry out in the new European project HIGHLIGHT. We realized preliminary characterizations on laser diodes emitting at 900nm, providing the building blocks for designing this new laser.

Keywords: tapered diode laser, GaAs, passive mode-locking, 2ph-FLIM

1. INTRODUCTION

We present the concept of a new laser source developed in the new European HIGHLIGHT project (“Highly Integrated Versatile Laser Source enabling two-photon excitation in digital diagnostics and biomedical research”) [1], [2]. HIGHLIGHT project objective is to realize a confocal microscope based on two-photon excitation fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (2ph-FLIM) with unprecedented image acquisition rates. The consortium of the project is formed by:

- III-V Lab in charge of the design, fabrication and tests of the diode laser
- Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK) in charge of the design, fabrication and tests of the detector, which is a Single-photon avalanche diode (SPAD)
- CSEM in charge of modelling the diode laser, tests the 2pm-FLIM with the laser, detector and samples of the project
- Vivascope in charge of integrating the whole experiment into the new microscope
- Brunel University of London in charge of validating the microscope on real sample for biomedical research

The developed microscope will be used in two specific applications: **i)** instant digital histopathology and **ii)** biomedical research in the context of cancer diagnosis. Nowadays, the best microscope has an image scan at 8 Mpixel/s, with 0.75 μm cellular resolution, but they can't perform 2ph-FLIM. HIGHLIGHT will make combine all this features: the additional 2ph-FLIM information will enable higher imaging depth in the tissue with the speed of a conventional microscope.

In this abstract, we will do a focus on the HIGHLIGHT diode laser. This compact source based on a tapered laser diode monolithically integrating several functions will address applications based 2ph-FLIM. This process comprises two phases: **i)** a pulse train excites the dye, **ii)** the laser is switched off to measure the fluorescence decay. This implies being able to precisely modulate the laser to switch from one phase to the other. The choice of the acridine orange dye for biomedical analysis means that a wavelength of around 900 nm has to be selected.

Next, we will present the concept of the diode laser able to perform the 2ph-FLIM in HIGHLIGHT project, then we will present characterizations on one and two-sections lasers to validate building blocks. Thus, we will present: measurements on the direct modulation of lasers, measurements of lasers with a saturable absorption section, followed by a parameters extraction. Then we will present the output power of ridge and tapered lasers while observing the beam quality.

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2. LASER SOURCE CONCEPT

We propose a monolithic mode-locked tapered laser diode producing pulse trains on demand that can be flexibly tailored to a specific fluorescent dye for time-resolved 2-photon excitation measurements at high data acquisition rates.

III-V Lab and CSEM demonstrated [3] a record pulse energy of 200 pJ with a pulse repetition frequency (PRF) of 3 GHz with a single monolithic mode-locked device: a long-cavity multi-section tapered laser diode, but without the possibility of fast ON/OFF switching of the pulse train. Following this pioneering demonstration, FBH recently published [4] a similar monolithic laser design with a pulse energy of 100 pJ and an FRI of 6 GHz. In the Table 1, we report this state of the art and we compared it to the objectives of HIGHLIGHT project.

Specifications	SoA for 100pJ monolithically mode-locked laser diodes			HIGHLIGHT ML laser
	MLSCL [3]	FBH [4]	FBH [5]	
Overall cavity length	13.5 mm	6 mm	6 mm	6 mm
Active gain medium	2x5 QW GaInAs/GaInAsP	2x6 nm QW GaAsP	1xN.A. nm QW GaAsP	2x5 nm QW GaInAsP/GaInP
Operation wavelength	990 nm	832 nm	780 nm	900 nm
2ph-FLIM FoM	4 nJ.W	4 nJ.W	13 nJ.W	13 nJ.W
Pulse energy	201 pJ	104 pJ	320 pJ	>160 pJ after GDD correction
Pulse peak power	18 W	40 W	40 W	80 W after GDD compensation
Pulse width	11ps (2ps after GDD corr)	2.6 ps	8 ps	2 ps after GDD compensation
Pulse Repetition Frequency	3 GHz	6.3 GHz	6.6 GHz	6 GHz
Pulse burst duration	Pulse burst modulation is not available			From 10 ns to continuous ML
Pulse burst turn-OFF time	Pulse burst regime not available			<0.3 ns

Table 1: State of the Art for 100pJ monolithically mode-locked laser diodes. Acronyms: SoA (State of the Art), MLSCL (name of a project on mode locked semiconductor lasers), FBH (Ferdinand-Braun-Institut), ML (Mode-Locked, QW (Quantum Well), GDD (Group Delay Dispersion).

The multi-section tapered laser diode developed will generate a train of short pulses (10 ps) at 6 GHz, with high peak power (>20 W). The source will also be agile: the pulse train can be switched on and off (On/Off switching) in less than 0.3 ns every 125 ns (8 MHz frequency).

The epitaxial structure (Figure 1) comprises a GaInAsP quantum well, surrounded by GaInP layers forming the optical cavity, with external GaInAlP confinement layers, all produced by metal-organic vapor-phase epitaxy (MOVPE).

Taking into account its thickness, the optical cavity is also called “Large Optical Cavity” (LOC).

The Quantum Well and the Optical Cavity constitute the core of the laser structure. III-V Lab is one of the rare laboratories in the world to have developed laser structures on GaAs based on semiconductor alloys without Aluminum in the active region of the laser, for a better reliability of the lasers.

When the QW is located in the centre of the optical cavity, we call this configuration a Symmetric LOC. When the QW is not located at the centre of the optical cavity, we call this configuration an Asymmetric LOC.

From a previous project, we have used two laser structures, one with a symmetric LOC and one with an asymmetric LOC. The thicknesses of the core layers are depicted in the Table 2 below. For both cases, the total optical cavity has a thickness of 900nm.

Optical cavity	Symmetric	Asymmetric
Top waveguide (P)	450 nm	225 nm
Quantum well	8 nm	8 nm
Bottom waveguide (N)	450 nm	675 nm

Table 2 : Core layers thicknesses

The targeted performance of the HIGHLIGHT source will be achieved by implementing a multi-section tapered laser geometry comprising the following sections (Figure 2):

- reverse-polarized, saturable absorber section for passive mode-locking operation,
- modulation section for pulse train selection (On/Off switching) at a frequency of 8 MHz,
- straight gain section for single-mode spatial transmission,
- tapered gain section for high optical power emission.

Figure 1: Epitaxial structure of the laser.

Figure 2: Schematic of the multi-section tapered laser

3. STUDY OF THE DIRECT LASER MODULATION

The pulses generated by mode locking should be switched on and off with a time of 0.3ns, which corresponds to a bandwidth of 1GHz. For this reason, we have checked the direct modulation bandwidth of 1mm long ridge laser, with HR/AR coated facets, from the two existing wafers, from a previous project, with symmetric and asymmetric LOC structures presented in the previous section. Table 3 below shows their threshold currents, external differential efficiencies and series resistances, which are very similar.

Optical cavity	Symmetric	Asymmetric
Threshold current	44mA	40mA
External differential efficiency	1.06W/A	0.93W/A
Series resistance	5Ω	5Ω

Table 3: Comparison of parameters extracted from L-I and V-I characteristics

We have characterized the scattering parameter S21 with a Vectorial Network Analyser Anritsu 37397C (40MHz-60GHz) and a high-speed photodiode Thorlabs DX30AF (30GHz bandwidth). Schematics of the characterisation is shown in the Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Schematics of the direct modulation set-up

In the Figure 4 below, we show the direct modulation responses of 1mm long ridge lasers, polarised at a current of 100mA, with symmetric and asymmetric LOC structures. The -3dB bandwidth are 2GHz and 3GHz respectively. The lower bandwidth achieved for the symmetric LOC structure is linked to a roll off, which is not observed for the asymmetric LOC structure. This roll off is due to the first order low pass filter caused by the transport time of carriers (mainly the holes) in the optical cavity.

In the Figure 5 below, we show the direct modulation responses of the same 1mm long ridge lasers polarised at a current of 160mA. No roll off is observed on asymmetric LOC structure. A bandwidth of 4.2GHz is achieved. On the contrary, the roll off on the symmetric structure as increased, limiting the bandwidth to 0.4GHz only. This is due to the increase of the resonance frequency, as the square root of the polarisation current I_{pol} minus the threshold current I_{th} . In consequence the roll off is not any more compensated by the resonance.

Figure 4: Direct modulation response of 1mm long ridge lasers polarised at 100mA.

Figure 5: Direct modulation response of 1mm long ridge lasers polarised at 160mA.

Following these experimental and theoretical results, we have chosen an asymmetric LOC structure for the HILIGHT source.

4. VALIDATION OF THE SATURABLE ABSORBER

To design the HILIGHT source, preliminary characterizations were carried out to extract key parameters and validate basic building blocks, such as the saturable absorber. Indeed, a saturable absorber is needed to produce mode locked pulses. The two section ridge is also useful to derive important parameters such as gain, gain and absorber recovery time, which are needed for the design of stable mode locking operation.

We have characterized as cleaved bi-section ridge lasers, emitting at 900nm, from a previous project, with a total cavity length of 1mm and different lengths of saturable absorber (0.1mm, 0.2mm and 0.3mm) biased at different reverse voltages (0V, -1V, -2V and -3V).

Figure 6 shows the schematics of the two sections ridge laser.

Figure 6: Schematics of a two sections ridge laser.

Typical optical power-current (L-I) CW characteristics at 20°C are shown in Figure 7 for an absorber length of 200 μm . The threshold current increases as expected with increasing reverse bias voltage.

Figure 7: L-I characteristics for different saturable absorber voltage for a symmetric structure (left) and an asymmetric structure (right). The length of the absorber section is 200 μm .

Increasing the reverse voltage from 0V to -3V results in an increase of the threshold current and of the power at breaking point, since more carriers have accumulated. Increasing the absorber length has the same effect. We notice also a very high external differential efficiency just after the lasing threshold and a hysteresis cycle. Both are typical of a laser with a saturable absorber.

For Labs=200 μm , L-I curves for asymmetric LOC ridge show much higher threshold currents and powers at breaking points. This difference is due to a lower modal gain of asymmetric LOC compared to symmetric LOC.

These results validate the performance of the saturable absorber.

In Figure 8 and Figure 9, we show the comparison of threshold current evolution and optical power at breakpoint with the reverse bias voltage applied to the 200 μm long absorber section, respectively. They show the highest sensitivity of the asymmetric LOC structures.

Figure 8: Comparison of threshold current evolution with bias voltage of saturable absorber

Figure 9: Comparison of power at breakpoint evolution with bias voltage of saturable absorber

5. PARAMETERS EXTRACTION FROM 1MM RIDGE LASERS

For modelling of stable mode-locking performance, optimization of the cavity geometry, a set of key laser parameters shall be measured. They are listed in Table 4.

We use single section and two section ridge waveguide (RW) laser structures with the cavity length of 1 mm. Two section RW laser has a short 100 to 300 μm length section near the back cavity facet (referenced as absorber independent of the applied bias) and a front gain section.

In the rate equation model used to interpret the measurements, we account for the current spreading and partial overlap of the optical mode with the gain QWs in the mode slow axis direction (in the epitaxial plane direction). The in-plane diffusion results in the carrier exchange between the QW regions overlapping and non-overlapping with the optical mode. The in-plane diffusion process is accounted for by the model in terms of characteristic in-plane escape and capture rates, which enable us to get an agreement between modal gain parameters of RW and broad area (BA) laser devices utilizing the same epitaxy.

Parameter	Name	Value
α_H	Phase-amplitude coupling	2.2
α_i	Intrinsic WG loss	2.6 cm^{-1}
ΓG_0	Logarithmic modal gain coefficient	28.5 cm^{-1}
n_{t_log}	Logarithmic transparency carrier density	$3.4 \cdot 10^{-18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$
J_t	Logarithmic transparency current density	92 A/cm^2
B	Radiative recombination coefficient	$6.4 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^3/\text{s}$
T_L	Differential carrier lifetime at threshold	1.5 ns
T_A	Absorber recovery time	0.45-2 ns for -3 to 0 V bias
$\tau_{D//}$	Effective escape and capture time due to in-plane diffusion	0.11 ns

Table 4 Key parameters measured

Figure 10 shows the extracted modal gain at the lasing wavelength of 905 nm vs QW carrier density and bias of the RW laser diode structure. The measurements are based on Hakki-Paoli method applied to a two-section laser yielding the net modal gain spectra of the structure. The structure is driven below the lasing threshold, with a fixed current on the gain section and varying absorber bias. In this configuration, the positively biased gain section is a source of ASE enabling the cavity net modal gain measurements even at large negative absorber biases. The gain spectrum of the gain section and the cold cavity losses are then subtracted from the net modal gain to extract the modal gain of the absorber section alone at a given bias.

Figure 10: Modal gain (left axis) and bias voltage (right axis) vs carrier density.

Figure 11: Differential carrier lifetime as a function of applied bias.

Both the differential carrier lifetime in the gain section and the absorber recovery time measurements are based on the pulsed current driving and account for the prevailing radiative recombination rate of carriers ($\propto Bn^2$) even at well below

the transparency carrier density. We also account for the finite settle time of the dynamic conditions due to driving electronics limitations, parasitic capacitance and inductance of the laser chip mounting and wiring as well as due to the series resistance and capacitance of the p-i-n junction itself.

The differential carrier lifetime in a single-section RW laser structure is measured along the lines of the conventional Adams' technique. Namely, we measure the delay time to the first lasing spike as a function of applied current and correcting this for the electronics transient time.

The absorber recovery time measurements utilize positive current pulses superimposed on the negative DC bias at the front section of the two-section RW structure. The other (back) section is positively biased and serves as a steady source of spontaneous emission (SE), like in our gain measurements. The applied current pulse to the front section is made sufficiently long to reach the steady-state amplification of SE. The absorber recovery time is then extracted from the decay of ASE at trailing edge of the applied current pulse. The detection is performed using time correlated single photon counting technique and the extracted recovery time vs bias is plotted in Figure 11 after the correction for the finite electronics transient time and the initial recombination rate of carriers $\propto Bn^2$.

6. VALIDATION OF THE OPTICAL POWER AND BEAM QUALITY OF THE RIDGE LASER

In the HIGHLIGHT source, both the modulation section and the straight part of the tapered laser use a ridge structure. Its ability to deliver high power in a high beam quality is of prime importance. Therefore, we have measured the CW L-I, V-I characteristics at 20°C, the far and near fields of a 2mm HR/AR coated ridge laser with an asymmetric LOC structure. Below, Figure 12 shows the L-I and V-I characteristics of such ridge laser.

From these characteristics, we can derive the following parameters: $I_{th}=32\text{mA}$, $\eta_d=0.98\text{W/A}$ and $R_s=1.9\Omega$.

Figure 12: CW L-I and V-I of 2mm long HR/AR ridge laser

We have measured the fast and slow axis far-fields from 100mA to 400mA, which are shown in Figure 13

Figure 13: Fast and slow axis far-field of a 2mm HR/AR ridge laser polarized at different currents

From these graphs, we derived the evolutions of Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) and full width at $1/e^2$, which are shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Evolution of far fields full widths in the fast and slow axis

In both directions, the far-fields show a single mode behavior. In the fast axis the full width at $1/2$ and $1/e^2$ are constant, with 31° and 57° , respectively. In the slow axis, there is a slight increase of the full widths, from 9° to 12° (FWHM) and from 16° to 20° (at $1/e^2$). This is a typical variation for a ridge laser, due to temperature increase below the ridge when current increases.

The near-fields have been measured at the same currents and show also a single spatial mode behavior. From the far and near fields full widths at $1/e^2$, we have calculated a beam quality parameter M^2 of 1.2 in the slow axis direction for an injected current of 400mA. The high beam quality achieved for an output power of 350mW validates the ridge structure.

7. TAPERED LASER

We have characterized two sections tapered lasers, emitting at 900nm, with an asymmetric LOC structure, from a previous project dedicated to time-of-flight LIDAR [6]. Figure 15 shows a schematic diagram of the tapered laser.

Figure 15: Schematic diagram of a tapered laser

The tapered laser has two sections: **i**) a straight, 1mm-long, narrow-width, index-guided, single spatial mode section for modal filtering, and **ii**) a tapered, 2mm-long, gain-guided section with a tapered full angle of 4° for high power.

We have measured the L-I and V-I characteristics of the tapered lasers under CW operation at 20°C (Figure 16).

Figure 16: L-I characteristics in CW regime of a tapered laser

From the characteristic with an injected current of 400mA in the ridge we derived the following parameters: $I_{th}=340mA$, $\eta_d=0.86W/A$, $R_s=0,3\Omega$, $P=0.8W$ at 1.5A, $WPE=28\%$ at 1.5A. We have measured the far-fields in fast axis (FA) and slow axis (SA), which are shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17: SA far-fields (left), SA far-fields widths evolution (middle), FA far-fields widths evolution (right)

The SA far-field widths decrease when the tapered current increase, reaching a low FHM value of 1.2° for a current of 1.6A in the tapered section. It may be due to the increase of the refractive index in the tapered section due to temperature increase.

The FA far-field widths are stable, with values of 31° and 57° identical to that previously reported for the 2mm ridge laser. We have also measured the SA near-fields at the facet and at the beam waist. Indeed, tapered lasers have got inherent astigmatism located inside the device at a distance from the facet $L_{waist}=L_{taper}/n_{taper}$.

We have then calculated the beam quality parameters in the SA.

Figure 18 shows the SA near field and the SA beam quality parameter M^2 evolutions with current in the tapered section.

Figure 18: SA near field at waist (left) and SA M^2 (right) evolutions with currents in the tapered section

For the currents $I_r=400\text{mA}$ and $I_t=1500\text{mA}$, giving the maximum optical power of 800mW , the SA M^2 value is 2.2, which is a reasonable value for a tapered laser.

8. CONCLUSION

The results obtained on the basic building blocks, saturable absorber, ridge laser and tapered laser, enable the HIGHLIGHT laser source to be designed, and show that they work in line with the desired objectives.

The saturable absorber operates as expected for both symmetric and asymmetric LOC structures. The direct modulation shows no roll-off and bandwidth of 4.3GHz for asymmetric structure. Single section 2mm ridge with asymmetric structure shows high optical power of 350mW in single spatial mode. An optical power on tapered lasers of 0.8W CW for asymmetric structures with $M^2=2.2$ is achieved.

Useful parameters for modelling of stable mode locking operation have been extracted.

Active regions have been designed (with variation of QW size and number), based on a asymmetric LOC structure. The epitaxial growth of these structures was performed in December

Design for stable mode locking operation is ongoing with requirement to get performances on 6mm length chip in the new material system. Characterizations of tapered lasers at higher optical power will be carried out in the near future.

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